

Genderstereotypen in der Archäologie? Wir dekonstruieren gängige Konzepte, diskutieren Genderdiversität und -fluidität in Gegenwart und Vergangenheit.

Gender stereotypes in archaeology? We deconstruct traditional concepts and discuss gender diversity and fluidity in the present and past.

Stéréotypes de genre en archéologie? Nous déconstruisons les concepts courants, discutons de la diversité et de la fluidité des genres dans le présent et le passé.

Freitag • Vendredi • Friday • 16–18h

- 08.03.24** - Stereotypes about Men and Women (Chapter 1–6)
- 22.03.24** - Feminist Perspectives (Chapter 7–12)
- 05.04.24** - Gender Binarity and Fluidity (Chapter 13–18)
- 19.04.24** - Researching Gender, Gendering Research (Chapter 19–24)
- 26.04.24** - Future Perspectives

Literatur • Literature (free download):

Coltofean-Arizancu, Gaydarska, Matic (eds.) 2021
L. Coltofean, U. Matic and B. Gaydarska, Gender Stereotypes in Archaeology – A Short Reflection in Image and Text. Leiden: Sidestone Press.

<https://www.sidestone.com/books/gender-stereotypes-in-archaeology>

Zoom-Link: <https://unibe-ch.zoom.us/j/63676339649>